

Synthesis and Magnetic Properties of Magnesium Ferrite Nanoparticles

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Magnesium ferrite nanoparticles were synthesized using co-precipitation and sol-gel methods. The nanoparticle samples were annealed at different temperatures in air for 4 hours. All the samples were single phase except the sol-gel sample annealed at 700°C which showed presence of α -Fe₂O₃. The grain size was found to be 28-33 and 15-50nm for these nanoparticle samples prepared by co-precipitation and sol-gel methods respectively. The magnetization value increased with the increase in annealing temperature in the samples prepared by co-precipitation method whereas the samples prepared by sol-gel method did not show any systematic variation. The highest magnetization values of 34 and 24 emu/g were observed at 300K for the samples annealed at 900°C prepared by co-precipitation and sol-gel methods respectively. The blocking temperature was found to be increased with the increase in grain size in the zero field cooled magnetic measurement. The observed magnetic behavior can be explained on the basis of different synthesis methods and grain growth in these samples.

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